

Sensational to Sensual

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Abstract

Fortunately or unfortunately, design can never leave anything alone, even if it is good enough. Design intervention is called for to effect change. Many a designer face this dilemma when confronted with good, judicious products which they would have liked to leave alone, but cannot, because design must be carried on. Incidentally, the above mentioned qualities are meanings of the word - 'sensible'. Design intervention can lead to the addition of sensational qualities, which can make it say loudly that 'it has been designed'. In this case the designers have to ensure that the design intervention is visible to the clients. The approach if taken to the extreme may lead to senseless or stupid products. On the other hand one may try to keep the sense in tact and yet go beyond it to achieve a quality of subtle awareness in the product, which harmonizes well with the environment and also makes an individual statement and create an aura of curiosity & mystery. One word that comes nearest to these qualities is 'sensual', which according to dictionary meaning is gratifying to the senses. And why shouldn't a product be like that.

In this paper the aspects of sensible, sensational and sensual attributes of products will be discussed and investigate what 'sensual' means and if it appeals to emotion universally. And if so, what methodologies can be adopted to create sensual products.

Generally it is difficult for designers to read papers in conferences, probably because design is a visual medium and translating it into another medium like written word leaves most of us cold. Nevertheless it needs to be done for the sake of developing theories of design, education, creating acceptance for design and above all communicating it to the people who do not understand visual language of design. The translation of visuals into words and vice versa is many times used as effective and integral part of design methodology – Design process starts with words and verbal articulation and is converted into a visual statement by the designer. The end of the process is not product or prototype, as is usually believed, but another set of words and verbal articulation, translating the visual design into words for presentation to the clients / customers. If the designs are too sedate, attempts are made to use words to give more verve and punch and in the process to sensationalize. This is often done by advertising people. In the next design iteration these punch lines / words may be translated back into the visual language of design, thereby products which have more verve and punch – sensational products.

I have titled of this paper ‘Sensational to Sensual’ to make it sound a little more sensational, because I want to put some punch into it to get your attention and raise some issues during the discussion that will follow. But that is not all to it. The title has come out of deliberation and thought on the subject, and feeling that words have power and if articulated, can have a bearing on the design outcome and the design process as well as methodologies. Many companies and designers attempt to use words to derive forms. Words like ‘security’, ‘pleasure’, ‘fun’ etc. are used by car designers to create forms that can evoke such feelings in their customers. How successful are they is for you to judge. And how this methodology can be made to succeed is for all of us to think.

‘Sensational’ and ‘sensual’ are emotive qualities - our responses to stimuli, which in case of design are largely ‘visual’. Of course, other qualities of products also contribute to these emotions. For example the ‘smooth writing’ of an ink pen, car ‘holding the road like dream’, ‘purr’ or ‘roar’ of a motorcycle engine, the ‘rustling sound’ of silk garment, ‘soft touch’ of velvet, and so on?

If we see around us, we are totally surrounded by designed environment, by whole lot of man-made objects and products. They all communicate to us providing stimulus to our senses. Some of these products or objects do fulfill the purpose for which they were designed. Some do not. Some fulfill other needs. Most of the products that we have around us are practical, judicious, reasonable, and perform fairly well. They make sense in the environment they are kept. Incidentally all these qualities are meanings of the word ‘sensible’. They are also ordinary products of day to day use without which we cannot do. They may therefore be labeled as ‘Sensible Products’.

Fortunately or unfortunately, design can never leave anything alone, even if it is good enough. Design intervention is called for to affect ‘change’. Many a designer face this dilemma when confronted with redesign commissions for fairly good, judicious products which they would have liked to leave alone, but cannot, because design must be carried on.. Design intervention has to lead to the addition of qualities which can make it say loudly that it has been ‘designed’. Designers have to see that design intervention is very visible to the clients – build some sensation into the design or make it sensational. These are the products which are loud, which create a strong impression, excitement or even horror. These could be termed as ‘Sensational Products’.

On the other hand, there are products which go beyond use, beyond function, beyond our accepted sense of aesthetics, which also inspire us. Besides performing well they create an aura of mystery, curiosity and beauty; products which blend harmoniously and yet make a statement of their own, and are gratifying to the senses. One word that comes nearest to these qualities is 'Sensual'. These products may therefore be termed as 'Sensual Products'.

The examples in each category are umpteen. A VW product like Golf is a good and a sensible product for us. Porsches & Ferraris go beyond their function towards the sensual. If we look at American cars of 1950s, some of them, with fins and chrome, could be termed as sensational. Many sensational products can be found in exhibitions, entertainment parks etc. where these qualities are required.

Can products be classified according to these attributes of sensual, sensible and sensational? I would like to share with you, my attempt to develop a 'design tool' termed as 3S scale (SsS), which I hope takes us a little forward in this direction. I draw a linear scale with one end representing sensual products or designs and the other end representing sensational products or designs and the middle representing sensible products or designs (fig.1). We can classify products or designs, and then, on this scale, position them according to these attributes. Highly sensual products are to be placed on the right and highly sensational products are to be placed on the left. The distance from the centre (position for the sensible) represents the intensity of sensual quality and sensational quality respectively.

Fig 1

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Figure 1

If we superimpose ‘level of interest’ generated by these qualities, we may find the levels of interest on the sensational side are high, compared to the sensual side, whereas purely sensible products illicit rather low interest - probably because of their staid, matter of fact and expected qualities (fig.2). Sensual side shows ‘lower interest’ levels as compared to sensational side as it takes time to decipher the qualities of the sensual product, probably because of element of mystery built into it. Therefore another parameter that needs to be added is ‘time’ – ‘level of interest retained over a period of time’. We will find that there is a reversal of interest over a period of time (fig.3). That is why we find that some trends or fashions loose their sheen in short period of time, and others become ageless designs with interest in them growing with time.

Fig 2

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Figure 2

Fig 3

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Figure 3

If we go beyond the extremities on either side of the 3S (SsS) scale, we will find that too much sensationalization, leading to senseless and stupid products, with a sharp decline in the 'level of interest' (fig.4). If we go beyond the extreme on the sensual side we enter into the realms of art and loss of some functionality. That is why we see products on this edge which have become object de art and are immortalized in museums around the world. Many of these products are failures in the market place.

If the linear scale is turned into a curve, we see sensational and sensual almost meet, a very thin line dividing the two (fig.5). We need to be highly sensitive to this line. That is why many a times, piece of 'junk' get passed on as artistic (arty) product and an 'artistic' product, with great reviews from designers / critics, gets low interest rating from customers. This graphic model seems to be nearer to the reality.

Fig 4

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Figure 4

Fig 5

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Figure 5

Fig 6
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Figure 6

If we look at some more properties, sensible products are typically contextual. They fit properly. They are often products of rigorous methodologies. Sensible products lend themselves easily to conventional design methodologies, which have been perfected since the days of Bauhaus, Ulm and to the present times. Many design schools lay great emphasis on the methodologies in their educational programs and with the help of techniques like market research, customer research, product planning, feature analysis, create many a sensible product. There are, however, mild echoes heard from time to time that these methods do not lead to extraordinary designs. These voices eventually die down, as there has been no breakthrough in developing methods to create sensual products (fig.7)

Fig 7
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Figure 7

To get an insight into the method of developing sensual products or even sensational products, I would like to study the methods used by makers of show products - show cars by car makers, ramp fashions by fashion designers. What drives them, what inspires them, what makes them select a design or reject a design when criteria are not so well defined like function, manufacturability, ergonomics, man-machine interaction? What methods to use when one has to work in the domain of 'feelings'? What to do when one has to work under the dictum - 'Form Follows Feelings'? I would like to see if some of these methods can be imbibed by product designers.

The question is - can we develop & use such methods? Is it possible? Would the products lose the very essence of sensuality, which we are trying to create by imposing a method on its process of creation? Should we leave it alone to the intuitive abilities of the designer, her experience, sensitivity and sensibility? In that case, where is its place in a design education program? Being a design educator & researcher, my position is that we cannot leave it alone; we must find answers.

Experimental methods

Here it will be right to mention the movements like Memphis, Alchemya lead by people like Sottsass, Mendini and other post modernists like Michael Graves who freed the products from the shackles of pure functionality. Alchemia group commissioned four different architects to design four legs for a single table. They opened up the minds to see the alternate possibility as viable, more universal and acceptable and thereby possibly Global. Many would of course dub their efforts as sensational. However, over the years many designers have regaled in this freedom to create sensual & global products.

Shift the context

Memphis products were often the 'products of experimental methods without carrying the burden of context, ethnicity etc'. It is not easy to unburden the mind from the shackles of context when the classical design training lays great emphasis on the context. Under the circumstances it may be strategic to shift the context and redesign. For example a solar cooker is a natural gadget for a tropical country like India with 300 days of Sunshine

available in a year. What could be done if a solar cooker has to work in Europe? If we work on this idea, we could probably make a much superior product for India

Reversing the design process

One of my students at AHO is designing ski gear for professional skiers. He is going about the design in reverse – brand and branding as the first step. He developed the brand around the legend of a place - Lyngen. The Lyngen community has special laws and rules as compared to the rest of Norway. It houses a military garrison. It has rugged landscape with steep ski slopes. From the name, he is building a logo, and only after that he will do the garment design. He talked to professional skiers - not about the garment or gear and its functional qualities, but how do they see themselves. ‘Knowledgeable about mountains’, ‘mentally strong and determined’, ‘physically strong with body control and flexibility’, ‘disciplined’ were some of the answers. This is not the regular method he adopted in the earlier projects, but hopes that this experimental methodology will open new insights about the product he is designing, and he is looking for breakthroughs.

Shadow watching

I have been talking to Jan Digerud, my colleague at AHO, Oslo, who delivered a lecture - Game of Observing - to my students. He argues that you see an object because of the shadow it creates. He wants the students to look at the ‘shadows’ that objects create, and start the process of design from there – ‘start from effect and design for effect’ . .

Free wheeling

Computers offer great possibility for ‘form free-wheeling’ – doing kind of things with forms that were unthinkable in the past. The commands like stretch, skew, distort, morphing, nerb pulling & pushing can change ordinary shapes into unconceived and interesting shapes. These are shapes generated without thinking of consequences. If one is not too much worried (an inhibiting factor) about the consequences (function, ergonomics, manufacturability etc.), one can generate a large variety of forms and variations, and possibly stumble upon an ‘extraordinary form’ from the generated pile. The designer will require a keen eye to pick a winner form the forms so generated, and develop it further to create a sensual product.

Freeing the mind

Many ancient meditation techniques have gained acceptability in the modern world as a means of relieving stress and improving physical and mental health – improving awareness, perception & creativity. Notable among these are Yoga, Tai-chi, Vipasana. There are studies, which have shown that these techniques reduce tension and improve concentration, creativity and sensory acuity. These techniques may help designers to take an intuitive leap into creating ‘extraordinary’ products.

Role of Ritual

After drinking tea in Japanese Tea Ceremony, one concentrates on the tea cup – looks at it from all sides, at the patterns, at the cracks, at the irregularities, in silence, with deep concentration and reverence, till the minute features of form and texture of the tea cup get revealed to the observer. Can this ‘ritual’ be extended to observe other products, which need to be judged visually? Can this ritual be used as a method for visual evaluation, and eventually a creation? So what is the method or ritual – look at the object (do not care for other criterion) for a long enough duration, and then again, and again, and again with concentration and reverence, till it starts revealing itself and communicating. The process is ritualistic, repetitive in nature, and therefore meditative (freeing the mind) aspects are built into the process. So to place a product in its correct position on the SsS scale, meditating on the object through ritualistic observation technique, as described above can help.

These are not comprehensive answers to the concerns raised above. They need further deliberation, experimentation and research, which can lead to better insights to help designers to move the products on the SsS scale from sensibility towards sensuality.